

ISic3329

I.Sicily inscription 3329

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

terminus

Material

sandstone

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2015.10.07 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Helorus

Place of origin (modern)

Eloro

Provenance

contr. Gioi, 2.5km west of Eloro (36.86588, 15.06989)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Noto, Museo Civico di
Noto

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI337251

1. δεύτερος
2. ποτικεφα
- 3.

Edition: PHI337253

1. ποτὶ Κεφαλᾶς (?)
- 2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645580

EDCS 70900819

PHI 337251

PHI 337253

Bibliography

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1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 52.0929.1

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